

SOCIAL INTELLIGENCE AS A FACTOR IN ENSURING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF TRAINING

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Annotation. This article carried out an experimental study of the theoretical definition and justification of the conditions for the formation of social intelligence as a factor of self-awareness of the teacher and their effectiveness. It also talks about the psychological and pedagogical conditions for the formation of social intelligence as a factor of self-awareness of teachers.

Key words: Intelligence, abilities, socialization, sociogenesis, methodology, social intelligence, the need for self-development, the need for self-development of social intelligence.

Social intelligence as an independent type was identified in the last decades of the 20th century (E. Thorndike) and increasingly attracts the attention of researchers who consider it both as an ability and as a personality trait. The problem of the essence, functions, formation and development of social intelligence has been subjected to deep analysis in foreign and domestic psychology (J. Guilford, N. Kantor, G. Allport, M. Sullivan, R. Sternberg, N. A. Aminov, Yu. N. Emelianov, V. N. Kunitsyna, M. V. Molokanov, D. V. Ushakov, etc.). In pedagogical science, the importance of social intelligence has also aroused interest in it among a number of researchers. An analysis of the formation of social intelligence in younger adolescents was conducted (E. V. Vatina). Its formation in older adolescents was studied (M. V. Odanovich). The development of social intelligence of children (I. V. Kharitonova) and adults (M. A. Lukicheva, O. Yu. Pavlova) in various activities is considered. But the development of the problem of social intelligence cannot yet be called active. Thus, many aspects of the formation of social intelligence of teachers have not yet become the subject of extensive study. One of them, which has not received sufficient development, is the question of the determining role of social intelligence in self-realization of a teacher. Meanwhile, studies of self-realization, which is currently becoming almost a cultural stereotype of developed countries, have acquired particular relevance in connection with the awareness of its significance for social and individual development (A. Maslow, K. Rogers, E. V. Galazhinsky, V. E. Klochko, O. M. Krasnoryadtseva, L. A. Korostyleva, S. I. Kudinov, D. A. Leontiev, etc.). The problem of self-realization is one of the most discussed in pedagogical research (T. I. Baryshnikova, E. P. Baksheeva, M. N. Mironova, S. A. Pyataeva, V. A.

Slastenin, etc.). The objective and subjective conditions of professional self-realization of teachers have been studied, and an analysis of the formation of professional competence of future teachers based on readiness for pedagogical self-realization has been given. But the role of specific internal factors of self-realization of a teacher, in particular such an important property as social intelligence, and the conditions of its formation need to be clarified, theoretically and empirically substantiated.

The problem of social intelligence, its formation and development is being studied in different pedagogical contexts. Researchers are interested in age and content-activity aspects of the problem: the development of social intelligence of preschoolers by means of psychogymnastics (I. V. Kharitonova), pedagogical support for the development of social intelligence of preschoolers (I. Yu. Isaeva), the formation of social intelligence of younger adolescents with underdeveloped cognitive activity (E. V. Vatina), the formation of social intelligence of older adolescents in the process of solving cognitive problems and overcoming personal, interpersonal difficulties (M. V. Odanovich) are considered. Studies have been conducted on the development of social intelligence of future teachers (M. A. Lukicheva) and social workers (O. Yu. Pavlova). The possibilities of pedagogical support for the formation of emotional intelligence - as a component of social intelligence - in children are being studied (K. S. Kuznetsova). Starting from the 19th century and to the present day, the study of intelligence has been intensively conducted within the framework of testological and experimental psychological directions. There are two positions of scientists in understanding the essence and structure of intelligence. Some believed that the test measures a single, basic, intellectual ability. Others believed that there is no single intelligence. Intelligence is a sum of independent intellectual abilities, factors. Among the latter are the ability to adapt to constantly changing conditions of the surrounding reality (J. Piaget), a set of behavioral skills (A. Staats, K. Fisher), the ability to control one's own behavior, adequately assess oneself and one's capabilities (R. Feuerstein). M.A. Kholodnaya identified regulatory properties in intelligence. She significantly expanded the interpretation of intelligence, including non-intellectual components (regulation, motivation, etc.). Since the concept of social intelligence was first developed in foreign psychology, let us turn to the analysis of works on the problem in this area of scientific knowledge. Consideration of some approaches implemented in the testological and experimental-psychological areas of studying intelligence made it possible to isolate the social aspects of functioning, nature, and factors of

its development. Despite the fact that social intelligence was not yet considered as an independent type, it was established that intelligence is not only cognitive, but also behavioral abilities that allow a person to adapt to the constantly changing conditions of the surrounding reality. Later, two components were identified in the structure of intelligence: "technological" and "social", and in them - the ability to practically solve a problem (the ability to clearly and distinctly understand the essence of the problem), verbal abilities (the ability to clearly and distinctly express one's thoughts), social competence (the ability to accept others as they are, to accept someone else's point of view, etc.). New approaches to the study of intelligence made it possible to carry out a scientifically substantiated division of practical intelligence into cognitive and social.

The concept of "social intelligence" was first introduced by E. Thorndike in 1920 to denote "foresight in interpersonal relationships." The author identifies two sides of social intelligence: behavioral and cognitive. According to E. Thorndike, there are three types of intelligence: - abstract intelligence as the ability to understand abstract verbal, mathematical symbols and perform any actions with them; - concrete intelligence as the ability to understand things and objects of the material world and perform any actions with them; - social intelligence as the ability to understand people and interact with them.

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